

1. I am age 18 or older, I have read and understood the above information and I wish to participate in the research and continue with the survey. *

Please read the statement carefully and only answer "yes" if you agree to all of the above. Your participation in this research is voluntary. You may discontinue participation at any time during the research activity. Your decision regarding whether or not to participate in this study will not result in any loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Educational background

2. What is the highest level of formal education that you have completed until now?

Mark only one oval.

High school diploma or GED

Some college

Associate and/or bachelor's degree

Bachelor's degree

Master's and/or professional degree

Doctorate

Prefer not to say

3. How many courses did you take in which you had to implement source code prior to participating in Girls Coding Day? *

If you do not remember a concrete number please provide an estimate.

4. How do you estimate your computer coding experience before GCD?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very inexperienced	<input type="radio"/>	Very experienced				

5. How do you estimate your computer coding skills compared to the other members in your mentor group at Girls Coding Day?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
None	<input type="radio"/>	Highly skilled				

6. How experienced were you using the following programming languages before attending Girls Coding Day?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very inexperienced	Somewhat inexperienced	Neutral	Somewhat experienced	Very experienced
HTML	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CSS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Python	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. If you are comfortable using any other programming language(s), please state them here.

8. Are you currently working for a company? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 9*

No *Skip to question 12*

Your current company

9. What is your company's realm?

Check all that apply.

Internet

Education

Finance

Culture/Communication

Other: _____

10. What is your role in your company?

Check all that apply.

Software Engineer

Marketing

Different IT related role

Other: _____

11. How many years have you been working in this company before you participated in Girls Coding Day?

Handout

The following questions are about the handout that was sent to you prior to Girls Coding Day. Please note that this research is independent of the Coding Girls' Club organization. NONE OF THE HANDOUT DESIGNERS WILL EVER SEE YOUR INDIVIDUAL ANSWERS.

12. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your PERCEPTION of the handout.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied with the handout.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My expectations towards content of the handout were met.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Installing the software required for GCD was easy based on the handout.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, it was easy to understand the handout.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your perception about the USEFULNESS of the handout.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
The handout improved my productivity during GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The handout improved my effectiveness during GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, the handout was useful during GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. In your opinion, what was good about the handout you received prior to Girls Coding Day?

15. What could be improved about the handout you received prior to GCD?

Mentoring
experience

The following questions are about your mentoring experience during Girls Coding Day. Please note that this research is independent of the Coding Girls' Club organization. NONE OF THE MENTORS WILL EVER SEE YOUR INDIVIDUAL ANSWERS.

16. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your IMPRESSION of your mentoring experience.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
The mentor and students ratio was sufficient.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was unsure whether I could ask my mentor for feedback when I needed it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My mentor solved my technical problems when they came up.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My mentor guided me to find solutions for my technical problems myself.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My mentor displayed patience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My mentor answered my question in a clear way so that I could understand her/him easily.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to the SUPPORT you got from your mentoring experience.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Having a mentor helped me learn new technical skills.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having a mentor provided me opportunities to learn/improve my knowledge on different technologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, having a mentor was effective for improving my technical skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

18. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your SATISFACTION towards your mentoring experience.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied with my mentoring experience.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having a mentor helped me recognize my personal strengths using technology.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having a mentor helped me become more confident in learning new technologies.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having a mentor encouraged me to pursue programming	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My expectations towards my mentoring experience were met.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19. In your opinion, what was good about your mentoring experience?

20. How could your mentoring experience be improved?

Kick-off party

21. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your perception of the USEFULNESS of the kick-off party.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
The kick-off party improved my productivity during GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The kick-off party improved my effectiveness during GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, the kick-off party was useful as a preparation for GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

22. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your SATISFACTION with the kick-off party.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied with the kick-off party.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My ideal outcome towards the kick-off party was achieved.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My expectations towards the kick-off party were met.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

23. In your opinion, what was good about the kick-off party?

24. What could be improved about the kick-off party?

Before Girls Coding Day

25. To what extent was your participation in Girls Coding Day motivated by:

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all	To some extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	Completely
Wanting to have fun	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to try out computer coding	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to learn new technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to meet new people	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to share my experiences with others	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to see what others are working on	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to do better in school	<input type="radio"/>				
Wanting to advance my career	<input type="radio"/>				

26. If your decision to participate in Girls Coding Day was motivated by any other means than the ones mentioned before, please enter them here.

27. What prevented you to engage in computer coding prior to Girls Coding Day? (if anything)

During Girls Coding Day

28. Which Girls Coding Day event did you attend ***Mark only one oval.**

- 2018/11/2 Hong Kong Baptist University
- 2018/11/2 Xi'an University of Posts and Telecommunications (西安邮电大学)
- 2018/11/2 Beijing Language and Culture University (北京语言大学)
- 2018/11/2 Sichuan International Studies University (四川外国语大学)
- 2018/11/2 Guangdong University of Foreign Studies (广东外语外贸大学)
- 2018/11/2 Central China Normal University (华中师范大学)
- 2018/11/2 Beijing Information Science & Technology University (北京信息科技大学)
- 2018/11/2 Minjiang University (闽江学院)
- 2018/11/2 Nanjing University (南京大学)
- 2018/11/2 Renmin University of China Suzhou Campus (中国人民大学苏州校区)
- 2018/11/2 Renmin University of China (中国人民大学)
- 2018/11/2 Peking University (北京大学)
- 2018/11/2 Zhejiang University (浙江大学)
- 2018/11/2 Chongqing University (重庆大学)
- 2018/11/2 Communication University of China (中国传媒大学)
- 2018/11/2 Chengdu University of Information Technology (成都信息工程大学)
- 2018/11/2 Hainan University (海南大学)
- 2017/7/1 Wuhan
- 2017/7/22 Shanghai
- 2017/8/27 Guangzhou
- 2017/9/17 Hangzhou
- 2019/10/29 Chengdu
- 2017/11/26 Beijing
- 2017/12/2 Beijing
- 2017/12/16 Shenzhen
- 2018/11/24 Dalian
- 2018/3/25 Wuhan
- 2018/3/31 Nanjing
- 2018/11/24 Chengdu

2018/11/24 Guangzhou

2018/12/23 Chongqing

2019/9/8 Beijing

29. If applicable, please provide the URL to any project you worked on during GCD (optional). We will use your project URL as an additional indicator of proficiency and will never make it public.

30. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your SATISFACTION WITH WHAT YOU LEARNED.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Learning how to build a website was easy.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, it was easy to build a website.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was satisfied with the website I built.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

31. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your **SATISFACTION WITH THE OUTCOME** you achieved.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree or agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I built the website I wanted to build.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My expectations towards my website were satisfied.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with the website I built.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

32. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your **GROUP MEMBERS**.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree or agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Everyone had a chance to express her opinion.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Everyone had a chance to ask questions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The group members participated very actively during the project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Overall, the participation of each member in the project was effective.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

33. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your INTERACTION WITH OTHER PARTICIPANTS outside of your group.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree not agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I was unsure if I could ask other participants for help	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I helped other participants if they asked me for help	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other participants helped me if I asked them for help	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The organizers encouraged participants to help each other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My mentor encouraged me to help other participants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

After Girls Coding Day

- 34.** Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your LEVEL OF COMFORT using the following technologies after Girls Coding Day.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am comfortable with writing programs in HTML.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am comfortable with writing programs in CSS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am comfortable with writing programs in PYTHON.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am comfortable with using GitHub.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

35. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your COMPUTER CODING CAPABILITIES after Girls Coding Day.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I could build a website if I had a lot of time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could build a website once someone else helped me to get started.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could build a website if I could call someone for help if I got stuck.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could build a website if I had only the language reference manual for help.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could build a website if someone showed me how to solve the problem first.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could overcome problems if I got stuck while working on a coding project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

36. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your CAPABILITY OF LEARNING A NEW PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE after Girls Coding Day.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I could learn a new programming language on my own.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could learn a new programming language if I had a lot of time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could learn a new programming language because Girls Coding Day helped me get started.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could learn a new programming language if I could call someone for help if I got stuck.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

37. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your ability to CONTINUE LEARNING computer coding after GCD.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I would be able to continue learning about computer coding after GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Continuing to learn about computer coding after GCD is entirely under my control.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have the resources, knowledge, and ability to continue learning about computer coding after GCD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Please click strongly disagree for this one.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

38. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your FUTURE INTENTIONS after Girls Coding Day.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I intend to continue learning computer coding rather than not continue learning it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I could, I would like to continue learning about computer coding as much as possible.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would come to future Girls Coding Day events.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would recommend Girls Coding Day to my friends.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Individual demographics and general feedback

39. In what year were you born?

40. Are you...?

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to self define
- Other: _____

41. Do you consider yourself a minority in the programmers' community?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

42. In your opinion, what was good about the Girls Coding Day you participated in?

43. What could be improved about Girls Coding Day?

44. Is there anything else you would like to tell us about your experience during the Girls Coding Day you participated in?

Thank you very much
for your participation!

If you would like to receive a copy of our final report of our study findings,
please follow this link and provide your email address.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms